

ABUSE AND ANOMALY DETECTION USING MACHINE LEARNING FOR GITLAB RUNNERS

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PROJECT SPECIFICATION

The Git Service at CERN provides a large-scale GitLab Runners infrastructure that supports CI/CD pipeline execution across the organization. Everyday, more than 50,000 jobs are executed across 10 dedicated GitLab runners clusters, each tailored to the diverse needs of the CERN community.

While this shared runners environment provides flexibility and scalability, it is not protected against misuse or malicious activity. Users may unintentionally or deliberately launch resource-intensive workloads that monopolize cluster capacity, resulting in reduced availability and degraded service quality for other users.

To address this challenge, we propose enhancing the system's monitoring and security capabilities by developing a Machine Learning based anomaly and abuse detection system.

ABSTRACT

This report describes the development of a prototype machine learning (ML) system designed to detect anomalies and potential misuse within the GitLab Runner infrastructure at CERN. Two complementary approaches were applied: a classical unsupervised model (Isolation Forest) and a deep sequence model (LSTM autoencoder). The system was trained on 45 days of Prometheus metrics (CPU and memory) and evaluated using synthetic anomalies such as spikes, bursts, flatlines, and noise. Results showed that the LSTM autoencoder generalized well, effectively capturing temporal workload patterns, while Isolation Forest provided a lightweight baseline that was especially effective for spike detection. While still in an experimental stage, the prototype highlights both the promise and the challenges of applying ML and DL in large-scale CI/CD environments, and points toward future steps such as integrating OpenSearch logs, improving interpretability, and enabling real-time detection for reliable and fair resource usage across CERN's shared computing platforms.

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 GitLab CI/CD Infrastructure at CERN

CERN's GitLab CI/CD infrastructure operates at a significant scale within the research community. It supports more than 17,000 active users and over 180,000 projects, forming the backbone of software requirements for physics experiments and organizational services. On average, more than 20,000 pipelines are triggered monthly, resulting in over 50,000 jobs executed every day.

To sustain this scale, CERN's GitLab team provides a variety of runners, each optimized for specific workloads (see Figure 1.1). Shared runners handle most standard jobs, Spark runners support data processing with Apache Spark, GPU runners accelerate workloads requiring high-performance computation and so on. This diverse runner ecosystem ensures flexibility and efficiency in meeting the needs of the CERN community.

Figure 1.1: Overview of GitLab Runner Types at CERN

1.2 Challenges in Ensuring Fair Usage of GitLab Runners

Despite its robustness, the shared runner environment at CERN presents ongoing challenges in ensuring fair usage within the CERN community. Because thousands of users share the same infrastructure, individual jobs may unintentionally or deliberately consume disproportionate

amounts of resources. Such workloads can degrade overall performance and, in extreme cases, render clusters unavailable for the majority of users.

The current monitoring setup is effective at collecting metrics but relies heavily on manual inspection to identify cases of unfair usage. To address this gap, we implemented a custom thresholding check as part of this project. In practice, anomalies were defined not only through ML scores but also with simple rules such as CPU usage above 80% or sudden spikes in resource consumption. While this provided a baseline for comparison, it underscored the need for more adaptive approaches that can capture subtle or evolving misuse patterns.

1.3 Motivation for Machine Learning Approaches

To address these challenges, there is growing interest in applying machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) methods for anomaly and abuse detection in CI/CD environments. Unlike static thresholds, ML-based approaches can adapt to evolving workloads and detect subtle deviations from normal behavior that may signal resource misuse or malicious activity.

In this project, we applied both a classical anomaly detection method (Isolation Forest) and a deep sequence model (LSTM autoencoder) to GitLab Runner workload metrics. Isolation Forest provides a lightweight baseline for detecting unusual patterns in aggregated data, while the LSTM autoencoder leverages temporal dependencies to identify irregularities through reconstruction error. Together, these methods demonstrate the feasibility of ML-driven monitoring and mark a step toward more adaptive and intelligent systems for safeguarding shared resources and ensuring fair access within the CERN user community.

1.4 Scope of the Report

This report presents the development and evaluation of a prototype anomaly detection system for GitLab Runners at CERN. The work is structured around three main aspects:

- Data Collection and Preparation: Gathering metrics such as CPU and memory usage from Prometheus.
- Prototype Model Development: Applying and evaluating both an LSTM autoencoder and an Isolation Forest model to establish baseline job behavior and detect anomalies.
- Preliminary Results and Insights: Assessing the prototype on collected data to evaluate its effectiveness in identifying resource anomalies and irregular job patterns.

It should be emphasized that this project remains at the prototype stage and has not yet been integrated into production. Moreover, the evaluation relied on synthetic anomalies, since real labeled misuse cases were unavailable during development and evaluation. The current focus is on demonstrating feasibility, identifying limitations, and outlining directions for future development.

2. MONITORING IN CI/CD: BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

2.1 GitLab Runner Architecture and Usage

GitLab Runners are lightweight agents that execute CI/CD jobs defined in GitLab pipelines. Runners support several executors, such as Shell, Docker, and Kubernetes, which define how jobs are run.

In the CERN environment, GitLab Runners are deployed exclusively with the Kubernetes executor. Each job submitted through GitLab is scheduled as a Kubernetes pod, providing strong workload isolation, efficient resource allocation, and seamless scalability. This approach enables the infrastructure to support a wide range of projects and users, from small-scale software builds to compute-intensive scientific workflows, while maintaining fairness and stability across the shared platform.

The overall workflow can be summarized as follows:

1. A user commits code and triggers a CI/CD pipeline in GitLab.
2. The GitLab Runner receives the job and schedules it as a Kubernetes pod.
3. The pod executes the defined stages (.i.e. build or test) in an isolated containerized environment.
4. During execution, system-level metrics (e.g., CPU, memory usage) are collected by Prometheus and logs are forwarded to OpenSearch.
5. These monitoring data sources provide the basis for dashboards, anomaly detection, and root cause analysis.

This pipeline ensures both operational efficiency and transparency, while laying the groundwork for applying machine learning-based anomaly detection methods.

2.2 Existing Monitoring and Abuse Detection Approaches

At present, anomaly monitoring and root cause identification in the GitLab Runner infrastructure at CERN rely primarily on two tools: Grafana Dashboards and OpenSearch Logs.

The GitLab team at CERN have developed a set of custom dashboards in Grafana. These dashboards visualize real-time metrics collected from Prometheus, including CPU and memory usage, job durations, job queue lengths, etc. Filters by runner type and project allow to quickly isolate suspicious activity. For example, dashboards can highlight infrastructure saturation, a growing backlog of pending jobs, or stressed CPU and memory resources (see Figures 2.1 - 2.3).

OpenSearch serves as the centralized storage layer for GitLab Runner job logs. It enables searching, filtering, and correlating events across different runners and projects, making it indispensable for root cause analysis once anomalies are identified. We aimed to evaluate the

existing OpenSearch Anomaly Detection plugin. To ensure a controlled environment, a dedicated cluster was set up with the required configurations, permissions, and a copy of the relevant logs. The plugin has great potential but with the logs available for GitLab runner from our end, we could not leverage the plugin's potential for anomaly detection in runners, however, it could be a great addition for anomaly detection in the GitLab application.

Together, Grafana and OpenSearch form the foundation of current monitoring at CERN. While effective for visualization and root cause analysis, these tools depend heavily on manual inspection, which can be time-consuming and make it difficult to capture subtle or evolving misuse patterns. This limitation motivates the application of ML based approaches for more adaptive and proactive anomaly detection.

Figure 2.1: Grafana dashboard visualization of runner infrastructure saturation

Figure 2.2: Grafana dashboard visualization of CPU usage, illustrating overconsumption

Figure 2.3: Grafana dashboard visualization of memory stress

2.3 Machine Learning for Anomaly Detection in CI/CD

Machine Learning (ML) has become an increasingly important approach for anomaly detection. In time-series monitoring, ML models can establish a baseline of “normal” activity and identify deviations without relying on rigid, predefined rules. Classical unsupervised techniques such as clustering, density estimation, and isolation-based methods (e.g., Isolation Forest) have been widely used to detect unusual jobs or workloads.

More recently, Deep Learning (DL) techniques have been applied to exploit the temporal dependencies inherent in sequential data. Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs), and in particular Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) autoencoders, have shown effectiveness in domains such as cloud computing, cybersecurity, and industrial IoT by detecting anomalies that develop over time. Their ability to model sequential patterns makes them well suited for CI/CD pipelines, where workloads often follow characteristic temporal structures.

In this context, the application of ML and DL methods to GitLab Runner monitoring represents a promising step beyond conventional threshold-based alerts. These techniques enable the early detection of resource misuse and irregular job activity, complementing existing monitoring tools. At the same time, prior work in related domains highlights both the opportunities and the challenges of deploying such methods at scale in production environments.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Data Sources

The primary data sources for this project are Prometheus and OpenSearch, both of which are widely used at CERN for monitoring and observability. Prometheus provides time-series metrics such as CPU and memory usage, average job execution durations, etc. These metrics are essential for capturing the resource utilization and performance characteristics of GitLab Runner workloads.

To facilitate data extraction, we first created a custom Grafana dashboard tailored to measure the fair usage of GitLab Runners (see Figure 3.1). This dashboard combined relevant Prometheus queries into a unified view of system activity. The underlying queries were then exported and used to pull datasets directly from the Prometheus. Since large queries risked overloading the API and crashing our scripts, we designed the extraction to fetch data in two-day intervals, which were then concatenated into a single dataset covering 45 days. This approach ensured both reliability and consistency between the visual monitoring setup and the training data used for anomaly detection.

OpenSearch complements Prometheus by storing detailed execution logs for each job, including executed commands, build stages, and error events. Although OpenSearch logs were not used in this prototype, they are planned for future work, as they provide valuable context for root cause analysis and can enrich anomaly detection with job-level details.

Figure 3.1: Dashboard for Anomaly Detection in Grafana

3.2 Data Preprocessing and Feature Engineering

Because the raw metrics had irregular sampling intervals, preprocessing was essential prior to model training. Metrics were resampled into fixed 5-minute intervals to ensure consistent temporal granularity across features. Each feature was standardized (zero mean, unit variance) to eliminate scale disparities between metrics (e.g., CPU fraction versus memory in MBs) and prevent bias in the learning process.

Feature engineering centered on constructing sequential inputs to capture temporal dependencies. A lookback window of 12 steps (equivalent to one hour of history at 5-minute resolution) was applied, so each training sample consisted of the previous 12 intervals. To systematically test anomaly sensitivity, controlled contamination was introduced into the datasets by injecting synthetic patterns such as spikes, bursts, flatlines, and Gaussian noise. This allowed us to evaluate the model's response to different categories of abnormal behavior.

3.3 LSTM Autoencoder Model

The primary anomaly detection approach employs a Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) autoencoder. This architecture compresses sequences of normal workload metrics into a compact representation and then attempts to reconstruct them. Sequences that deviate from the learned baseline produce higher reconstruction errors, which are interpreted as anomaly scores.

For comparison, a classical unsupervised method - Isolation Forest (iForest) - was also evaluated. Unlike the LSTM, iForest does not exploit temporal dependencies but instead isolates points in the feature space. Its efficiency and simplicity make it a useful benchmark.

3.4 Prototype Pipeline Setup

The prototype pipeline was designed with reproducibility, transparency, and experiment management as guiding principles. Figure 3.2 illustrates the overall system workflow. Metrics are collected from Prometheus, which are visualized through Grafana dashboards and forwarded to a Spark-based preprocessing stage that executes every five minutes. The preprocessed data is then used for model inference in MLflow, and alerts (including pod IDs) are sent to Mattermost to provide timely feedback to the team.

Experiment tracking was facilitated by MLflow, which recorded model artifacts (weights, parameters), preprocessing standardizers, and evaluation metrics. Its experiment registry enabled direct comparison of runs and systematic tracking of improvements over time.

This pipeline establishes a flexible foundation for advancing toward a production-ready anomaly detection service, with future enhancements such as real-time scoring and deployment at scale across CERN's GitLab Runner clusters.

Figure 3.2: Overview of the prototype system workflow

4. PROJECT PROGRESS AND RESULTS

4.1 Dataset Preparation and Statistics

The datasets for this project were derived from Prometheus metrics collected across CERN's GitLab Runner clusters, with a primary focus on CPU and memory utilization. All metrics were resampled into fixed 5-minute intervals, creating a consistent temporal resolution across features. To prevent scale imbalances between CPU fractions and memory values, each feature was standardized to zero mean and unit variance.

To systematically assess detection capabilities, controlled contamination was added to the test datasets. Synthetic anomalies included spikes, bursts, flatlines, and Gaussian noise, each simulating a distinct type of misuse or resource abuse. Contamination was applied separately to CPU and memory files at rates of about 5%. This provided a controlled environment for evaluating model sensitivity to different anomaly classes.

4.2 Model Training and Evaluation

As described in Section 3.3, the LSTM autoencoder was implemented for sequence-based anomaly detection. The model was trained on standardized datasets using one hidden layer of 32 units, dropout regularization (0.2), and a stride of 1. Training was performed for 30 epochs with the Adam optimizer (learning rate = 0.001). Evaluation metrics included mean squared error (MSE), root mean squared error (RMSE), and reconstruction error quantiles (95th, 98th, 99th percentiles) to capture tail behavior.

Results showed a training loss of ~ 0.48 and a validation loss of ~ 0.29 , with RMSE values of 0.69 (train) and 0.54 (validation). The close alignment between training and validation errors suggests good generalization, while reduced reconstruction errors compared to earlier runs indicate that the model effectively captured normal workload patterns. Error quantiles (q95-q99 in the range 2.05-5.74) confirmed that most sequences were reconstructed with low error, while anomalous windows remained clearly distinguishable in the higher tail (see Figure 4.1).

Figure 4.1: MLflow experiment view showing LSTM autoencoder parameters and evaluation metrics

The Isolation Forest baseline was trained with 400 estimators and a contamination prior of 5%. Approximately 4.4% of training windows exceeded the anomaly threshold, consistent with expectations. While iForest lacks temporal memory, it provided a lightweight benchmark and was particularly effective for abrupt spikes.

4.3 Anomaly Detection Experiments

Detection experiments were conducted on both clean and contaminated datasets. On normal test data, the LSTM autoencoder produced very low anomaly fractions, confirming that it did not over-flag healthy workloads. With reconstruction errors concentrated around a mean of ~ 0.45 (std ≈ 1.03) and low validation loss (~ 0.29), the majority of windows were well reconstructed.

When synthetic anomalies were injected ($\sim 5\%$ contamination), detection rates increased in line with expectations. For example, in the memory usage dataset, injected anomalies raised the reconstruction error into the higher quantiles (q95-q99 = 2.05-5.74), making them stand out clearly against the normal baseline distribution. This demonstrated that the model could effectively separate anomalous windows from typical workload behavior.

The Isolation Forest (iForest) baseline showed similar trends but was generally less effective for temporally dependent anomalies such as bursts or flatlines. It was, however, more responsive to abrupt spikes. This highlights the complementarity of the two approaches: the LSTM

autoencoder excels at capturing sequential context, while iForest offers efficiency and quick anomaly scoring.

4.4 Observed Challenges and Limitations

Several challenges emerged during the project, spanning data preparation, model development, and infrastructure setup.

On the data side, the analysis was based on approximately 45 days of Prometheus metrics. While this was sufficient for a prototype, the relatively short observation window limited exposure to seasonal workload patterns and rare anomalies, reducing the diversity of training data. In addition, raw streams contained irregular sampling intervals and imbalances between features (e.g., CPU fractions vs. memory values), which complicated preprocessing. Windowing further reduced the number of usable validation sequences.

From a modeling perspective, tuning the LSTM autoencoder was non-trivial. Validation metrics fluctuated due to limited data variability, making it difficult to identify a stable “best” configuration. The Isolation Forest baseline, while simple to deploy and effective for spikes, proved highly sensitive to its contamination parameter. Although only a basic configuration was tested, more extensive hyperparameter optimization could significantly improve performance.

Finally, evaluation was constrained by the absence of real anomalies. Synthetic contamination provided a useful testbed for controlled experiments, but it cannot fully capture the complexity of real misuse scenarios. Interpretability also remains a challenge: Isolation Forest anomaly scores are opaque, while LSTM reconstruction errors highlight anomalies without revealing their underlying causes.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

5.1 Summary of Contributions

This project developed and evaluated a prototype anomaly detection system for GitLab Runners at CERN. The key contributions are:

- Data integration and preprocessing: Collected and standardized metrics from Prometheus and constructed time-series datasets enriched with synthetic anomalies.
- Prototype model development: Implemented and evaluated two complementary approaches to anomaly detection - an LSTM autoencoder for temporal modeling and an Isolation Forest for lightweight unsupervised scoring.
- System workflow design: Built a reproducible pipeline using MLflow, integrated with Spark for preprocessing, and Mattermost for alerting.
- Evaluation and insights: Demonstrated that the prototype can detect both injected anomalies and irregular workload patterns, outperforming static thresholding in flexibility and adaptability.

Overall, the work provides a foundation for extending anomaly detection capabilities within CERN's GitLab Runner ecosystem, complementing existing monitoring tools such as Grafana and OpenSearch.

5.2 Next Steps for Production Deployment

While the prototype confirmed the feasibility of ML-based anomaly detection, several steps remain before deployment at production scale:

- **Extended data coverage:** Collect at least 6-12 months of Prometheus and OpenSearch data to capture seasonal usage patterns and rare anomalies.
- **Hyperparameter optimization:** Apply automated search methods (e.g., grid search, Bayesian optimization) to refine LSTM and Isolation Forest configurations.
- **Hybrid detection strategy:** Combine static threshold checks (for clear-cut cases such as CPU > 80%) with ML models for subtler anomaly detection.
- **Exploration of alternative models:** Extend the study to other anomaly detection methods such as Matrix Profile or more advanced deep learning architectures, to compare performance and robustness across approaches.
- **Integration of OpenSearch logs for security:** Incorporate job-level logs into anomaly detection to increase visibility into what commands were executed within GitLab Runners. This would allow not only resource misuse detection but also early identification of potentially malicious or suspicious command sequences.
- **Alert calibration and interpretability:** Define anomaly score thresholds that balance sensitivity and false-positive rates, and develop tools to explain flagged anomalies.
- **Scalability and real-time inference:** Move toward streaming-based preprocessing and inference, enabling near real-time alerts integrated with CERN's monitoring stack.

These steps will help transition the system from a prototype to a reliable production system capable of protecting shared CI/CD resources and ensuring fair usage across the CERN community.

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